

Science in the Attention Economy

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“You know the rules, Publish or Perish.”

“But I have Published ... a lot in fact.”

“New Rules:

Publish, Publicize, and Hype or Perish.

Didn't you get the memo? Shame ...”

The new rules of academic success in the attention economy.

Twenty-five years ago, it was projected that, in an ever more interconnected world, money would no longer be the prime currency, attention would [1]. This would reshape social values and as we became more engrossed in efforts to gain attention, we would shortchange those around us; the drive for self would come at the expense of concern for the other. The projection has played out as prophetic and the attention economy is here, with its associated societal shifts.

Science and scientists are part of society. Neither sit on a lofty perch that makes them impervious to societal shifts. More than fifty years ago, it was projected that, as science grew larger, its structure would shift from community driven to individual driven [2]. Along the way, there would be a rise in quantitative metrics to evaluate scientists. Initially, metrics were limited to attention amongst peers, via citation counts. That has expanded. The attention a scientist's work gains from the public now plays into its perceived value. Scientists list media exposure counts on resumes and many PhD theses now include the number of times a candidate's work has appeared in popular science press. Science has succumbed to the attention economy.

Scientists have always wanted to have their work noticed. That's not new. However, when attention becomes currency, the ecosystem changes. The changing ecosystem encompasses universities, academic publishing, and the way science is communicated to the public.

Universities have adopted business models that follow economic market forces [3,4]. As the market has become one of attention, universities have dived headfirst into attention games. Faculty now receive messages to “brag about yourselves”. The bragging increasingly focusses on how much attention faculty work draws from the media (the rise of altmetrics is telling [5]). Universities encourage science faculty to become self-promoting entrepreneurs in the attention market and the value of a scientific paper is connected to

how much attention it garners. That attention, in turn, feeds into a universities academic profit (e.g., rankings, external funding).

Academic publishing is now dominated by for-profit companies. Revenue from subscriptions and from authors, who pay to be published, are no longer the only profit sources. More attention for papers in a publisher's portfolio of journals is currency. Publishers provide authors with game plans for getting their papers attention on social media, popular science press, blogs, podcasts etc. These attention generating schemes are packaged by publishers using the phrasing of "get your science the attention it deserves" (readers can key that phrase into google – we got over 500 million links). Scientists gain career benefits by participating in these schemes (metrics go up). The public is also exposed to more science. But all parties should remain clear sighted that publishers do profit from the attention (by association, research that can gain more attention is more profitable).

This brings us to science communication in the attention economy. Historically, scientists would communicate results to their scientific communities. Once properly assessed, verified, or refuted, influential results would gain traction (this requires time). Those that were breakthroughs were proclaimed as such to the public (and the contributions of others were acknowledged). Inject the attention economy into the ecosystem and things change. Results are now presented to the public as influential well before community assessment can take place. What turn out to be small findings and/or non-reproducible results are hyped as significant enough to share with the public. The drive for attention leads to a framing of results in a way that downplays uncertainty and viable alternative hypotheses (i.e., shortchanges the other). It also devalues studies that reproduce previous results (those do not garner attention).

The above feeds into several crises in science: Reproducibility crisis; Hyped results that fall short; Hyper-competition amongst scientists; Increasing retractions of published results [6,7,8]. It also leads to an uncoordinated deluge of science results, all proclaimed as breakthroughs, being blasted to the public under the pretense of public education. The people blasting the results do so with the thought that they deserve the attention. Deserve is a step away from 'entitled to' and people who feel they are entitled tend to have little concern for the other [9]. A large portion of the public, who are part of the other, will grow weary. Deteriorating trust in science can follow.

And herein is the paradox of science in the attention economy: *The things that are seen as being of value to individual scientists or institutions (e.g., 'getting the attention you deserve') are undermining public trust and devaluing science as a collective resource (i.e., as a common good).* This can push science toward a tragedy of the commons in which individual actions, done with no ill intent, can cause a collapse of a common resource or, at the least, a systemic restructuring of science as a societal resource [10].

Why should you, a member of the general public, care about any of this? Because you are part of the system - a consumer in the science attention market – and there is value in consumer awareness. As with other goods, advertising of science in the attention market will not go away. By the same token, as members of the general public, in the attention economy, we have become more attuned to separating advertising from badvertising, aka "cheap talk" [11,12]. The same can be done for the range of science results presented to us as significant. Look for the tell-tail signs that the goal is less about conveying information and more about garnering attention (e.g., overly positive wording, confident predictions,

downplay of uncertainty, no discussion of viable alternative hypotheses, of whether results have been reproduced or verified, a marketing of scientists from an institution versus a discussion of the science they are involved in – along with credit to scientists not at the institution).

If we remain cognizant that our attention is currency, and that it is not an unlimited resource, then we can use it wisely. This will also help individual scientists, journalists, and/or institutions from shortchanging the other that is the collective of science itself.

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Adrian teaches modeling & design, visualizing nature, and planetary science at Rice University. He was born in Zagreb, Croatia (rarely misses a Croatian soccer match). His BSc is from UW-Madison, where he was an art major before switching to physics. His PhD is from UCLA, where he was introduced to planetary science (as well as surfing). He was a president's postdoctoral fellow at UC-Berkeley (snowboard days) before coming to Rice. Adrian's scientific research relates to understanding interactions between the Earth's interior & surface environment, modeling, and multiple tangent meanderings. He is part of a first prize winning art-car team & recipient of the mayor's award, from the Jamail skate park, for most improved skateboarder over 30.

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Johnny served as a Sergeant in the Army, specializing in intelligence analysis, during the Iraq war. He received degrees in geophysics from the University of Houston (BSc) and Rice University (PhD). He is a modeler at heart and enjoys finding connections within and between different systems - science, society and religion. In his spare time he runs, probably too much, enjoying it most when on the trails with his dog and family. He is in the midst of a career change, having accepted a job as a data scientist at Los Alamos National Lab.

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